

Historical Background of Indian Education

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Summary

Before independence, Indian education has passed through four major periods. Vedic period, post Vedic period, Buddhist period, Muslim period and British period. Vedic period education of ancient India was integrated with Indian knowledge and science. Which was called 'Vidya'. This Vedic education of ancient times not only flourished Indian culture but also preserved it for the future. In post Vedic period education, provision was also made for caste based vocational education. Due to which India moved towards economic prosperity. The education of that time was also influenced by the Buddhism that emerged from Mahatma Buddha. The aim of Buddhist education was to create peace loving Satvik persons. In the last phase of the twelfth century, Mohammad Ghorī defeated the Delhi emperor Prithviraj Chauhan and laid the foundation of Muslim rule in India, after which various Muslim dynasties ruled India for about 550 years. During this long period of Muslim rule, Indian education was influenced and the education of this period was called Muslim period education. After the fall of Bahadur Shah Zafar, the last ruler of the Mughal dynasty in the 17th century, the British established their supremacy in this country and made the education of this country a medium to propagate their Christian religion, culture and English language. Looking at this historical background of Indian education, it can be concluded that the cultural and political conditions of the society of that time have a great influence on education. Indian education was also not untouched by this.

Key words: transition, duality, individual, whole, beyond, beyond, inhabitant of the end, salvation, ritual, transition, interval, discharge, view of the lion.

Historically, from ancient times till now, Indian life has passed through four major periods. In the first period, Indian philosophy of life has been influenced by spirituality. In the second period, Muslim culture got transferred to Indian culture. In the third period, European culture influenced Indian philosophy of life and in the fourth period, when Indians got independence, a new philosophy of life was created. In which there is a mixture of the civilizations of the east and the west. A culture developed in a coordinated form of spirituality, materialism, modernity, antiquity, machine power-mantra power etc. which is neither completely Indian nor completely western. The present Indian philosophy of life is suffering from this duality.

The education of that time has also been influenced by the changing Indian philosophy of life. On this basis, historically the background of Indian education can be divided into the following parts- Vedic education, post Vedic education, Buddhist education, Muslim education and British education. This time flow of Indian education is being analyzed as follows-

Vedic period education-

In the historical sequence, Vedic education is the first and ancient form of education system of India. The Vedic education system of India, based on the Vedic culture, was not a borrowed education system from any foreign power but was its own original system. The Vedic education system, originating in ancient India, focused on holistic development, moral and spiritual growth, and preserving cultural heritage. It emphasized character building, ethical conduct, and the pursuit of knowledge, with the ultimate goal of self-realization (Moksha). The system was characterized by the Guru-Shishya Parampara (teacher-student relationship) within Gurukuls, where students lived with their teachers and learned through oral traditions and practical experiences. In this era, the general public believed that education is the backbone of the all-round development of the individual and the society. We find evidence of this in ancient literature. Bharthari says in his 'Nitishatak'-

Knowledge is the friend of people when they go abroad, knowledge is the supreme god.

Knowledge is worshiped in kings, not wealth, and without knowledge an animal.

In the Vedic period, education was considered to be a source of light and power that transforms and improves our nature by harmoniously developing our physical, mental, material and spiritual powers.

In the Vedic period, the entire education was called 'Vidya'. Two forms of this Vidya were prevalent - 'Para' and 'Apara'. Para Vidya was related to the worship and meditation methods of Brahma and Apara Vidya was related to various means and activities to keep the social system well organized.

From the point of view of education system, all the educational work was done in Gurukuls and Rishi Ashrams. After the Upanayan ceremony, the student used to enter these Gurukuls and Rishi Ashrams to acquire education and used to live a life of complete celibacy and self-discipline for twenty-five years of his life and receive education from the Guru through oral method. At these natural education centers, all the subjects like philosophy, grammar, astrology, art, verse, dance, music, etc. were included from the point of view of both spiritual (para) and worldly (apara) knowledge. By spending a part of life at one place, Gurukul used to take the form of a family. In which all the residents considered the Guru as their spiritual father and had reverence for him and the Guru used to love his disciples like a son and paid attention to their all-round development. That is, the relationship between teacher and student used to be affectionate and close which remained in their future life also.

From the system, nature and objectives of education during the Vedic period, it becomes clear that the education of ancient times not only nurtured the ideals of Indian culture but also secured Indian culture for the future by creating a society in accordance with Indian culture.

Features of Vedic Education

Vedic education, as most people conceive it, is not a religious form of education. During the time at Gurukul, the students were taught free of cost, and guru (teacher) and shishyas (students) used to accommodate at the same place (gurukul). The Vedic education system focused on the comprehension of Vedic texts, and it points more toward religious neutrality. It, furthermore, practiced independence among students. Below are some features of Vedic education that make it relevant even in the 21st century:

1. Personality Development

Character building and personality development were the prime focus of Vedic education. The amount of stress given to personality development during the Vedic education period is incomparable to any other era. Morality was indispensable in ancient India. Students were taught to practice moral values throughout their lives. Teachers also focused on the learning of attaining sensorial control to facilitate character development. Self-dependence and simple life were promoted widely for the character formation of the students. They were called Brahmacharis during their learning period and avoided any luxuries or pleasures of life.

2. Practical Education

Vedic education did not only involve theoretical learning from religious scriptures like Mahabharata and Ramayana; it also paid attention to developing practical expertise. Children were taught to do manual work and other vocational training was also involved during the learning. A few vocations included weaving, pottery, etc.

3. Spiritual and Religious Values

During ancient times, instilling students with religious values was considered pivotal in education. Religious values and knowledge were entwined during the time. The Vedic education system, apart from instilling moral values in students, is also centered on establishing piety and religious values

among students. Education without spiritual and religious values was not considered education at all during that time.

4. Civic Responsibilities and Social Values

The students of Vedic education also had civic responsibilities. After gaining education in the Gurukul, they had to go back to society and help it in different ways to make it better and more evolved. They had to be hospitable and charitable toward needy people.

5. Enlightenment

Another objective of the Vedic education system was to teach students the importance of both body and soul to achieve ultimate enlightenment. The spiritual elements infused in the system, like chanting prayers and following religious rituals on important occasions, focused on the enlightenment of a human being.

Methods of Vedic Education

1. Recitation and Memorization
2. Introspection
3. Discussion
4. Travelling
5. Practical Exposure

The main objective of education during this period was to acquire Brahma Gyan. Through education, a person would go beyond external worldly attractions and gain knowledge about 'Brahma' through self-organization and concentrated thinking.

Buddhist period education-

After the Vedic period, Hindu religion had become distorted due to the prominence of yagyas and rituals among the Brahmin class. Animal sacrifice in yagyas and rituals had led to the prevalence of immorality and sin in the society, which had started creating discontent in the minds of the people. In the later period, Mahatma Buddha, seeing the anguish and discontent in the minds of the people, initiated a new religion based on human emotions like non-violence, kindness, charity etc. This new religion originated by Mahatma Buddha was based on Hindu religion (Buddhism) itself.

During this period of transition, the nature of education changed and a new education system was started which was called 'Buddhist education'. This Buddhist education system was different from the education system of the Vedic period. Buddhist education developed an education system which was a rival of the Brahminical education system, but was also similar to it in many ways. Buddhist education spread in Buddhist monasteries and Viharas. In these monasteries and Viharas, a person of any caste, religion, sect could accept Buddhism and get education by becoming a 'Shramana'. The task of imparting education was done by Buddhist monks. In these Buddhist Viharas, there was a system of both primary and higher education. Higher education was given only to Buddhist monks. The education of the then Buddhist monasteries and Viharas attracted not only Indians but also foreigners.

This was also a centre of attraction. In terms of purpose, the main aim of Buddhist education was to create people with pure and satvik character. The aim of Buddhist education was also to propagate and spread Buddhism through education.

Muslim period education-

In the eighth century, considering India as the 'golden bird', foreign Yavana powers started attacking this country. Initially, the aim of these foreign invaders was only to loot the wealth of the glorious India. But in the last phase of the twelfth century, Mohammad Ghori attacked India and defeated the then Delhi Emperor Prithviraj Chauhan and laid the foundation of Muslim rule in India. After this, many Muslim dynasties ruled India for about 550 years. In this period, these fanatic Muslim rulers completely Muslimized Indian education, culture and civilization. In the heat of fanaticism, famous educational centers like Nalanda and Takshila were destroyed and in their place Maktabas and Madrasas of Muslim culture and education were established. This new education system forcibly implanted by foreign Yavana powers was called the 'Medieval Muslim Education System'. The ideology of these Muslim rulers regarding education was so narrow that non-believers were not given a place in the then Maktabas and Madrasas. Apart from a few exceptions, Muslim education was only for those who converted to Islam.

In the Muslim era, 'Maktab' was built for primary education and 'Madrasas' for higher education. In this era, before starting education, the student had to be cultured with the 'Vismillah' sanskar. The objectives of education during this era were determined in accordance with Islamic civilization and

culture. The aim of the Muslim rulers was to spread Islamic law, Islamic political principles and Islamic social customs through Islamic education. Thus, education during the Muslim era was full of religious tendencies, which influenced Indian culture but could not be completely successful.

British period education-

After the fall of Muslim rule, India became the centre of attraction for European traders in the 17th century. Dutch, French, Dane, etc. missionaries propagated Christianity in this country through trade and used education here as a medium for this work. At this time, Muslim education established by Muslim rulers was moving towards degradation due to lack of proper protection. Taking advantage of this situation, these Christian missionaries initiated a new education for the propagation of Christianity. The British gave a new form to Indian education by establishing Calcutta Madrasa (1781 AD), Banaras Sanskrit College (1791 AD), Fort William College (1800 AD) etc. to satisfy both the Hindu and Muslim sections of India. In 1792 AD, the directors of the East India Company issued an order in 1813 AD on the basis of Charles Grant's report. In which it was recommended to spend Rs. 1 lakh per year for the promotion of Indian knowledge. This order later became a controversy of Eastern-Western education. To resolve this, Lord Macaulay sent a statement to the Company Government in 1835 in which he emphasized on English education. On 07 March, 1835

The British Government accepted Lord Macaulay's concept of education and determined the education policy of India and declared that the best use of all the funds allocated for education can be made only for English medium education.

The British government conducted a new experiment in education and decided that English education should be given only to the rich upper class Indians. When the upper class people get English education and get influenced by Western education, the lower class will automatically get influenced by them and start imitating Western culture. This experiment became famous in the British rule as the 'Nisyandan Siddhant'. The use of this principle related to education led to the creation of a class in India which was Indian by birth but became English by culture. Still, the dream of the British government that the common class would also be influenced by this elite English educated class could not be fulfilled. Because this was a class which lived in its own world, separate from the common people and was always trying to get the blessings of its ruler.

When the 'Nisyandan Doctrine' failed, Charles Wood (1854) presented his manifesto and tried to solve the problems of Indian education by focusing on them, but instead of trying to mold education according to Indianness in terms of Indian culture and ideals, he encouraged western education more. For this reason, the Indian public, under the leadership of Indian thinkers Swami Dayanand Saraswati and Swami Ramakrishna Paramhans, strongly opposed Wood's manifesto, as a result of which a commission was formed in 1882 under the chairmanship of William Hunter. The suggestions given by this first Indian Education Commission of the British period were based on Wood's manifesto, but they were presented in such a way keeping in view every aspect of Indian education that Wood's manifesto got a new life. As a result, there was educational awakening in India and the decisions of this commission influenced India's education policy till 1902.

Thus, Indians started opposing British-era education from 1857 AD along with the freedom movement. But the diplomatic tactics of the British rulers always tried to impose English education inspired by Western civilization on Indians. The purpose of the education commissions and committees formed by the British government from time to time was to strengthen their roots through education rather than to reform Indian education in accordance with Indianness. But the diplomatic evil intentions of the British government could not remain hidden from the eyes of aware Indian leaders, the result of which emerged in the form of the National Education Movement.

Educationa in independent India

In post-independent India, the education system underwent significant reforms with the goal of creating a more inclusive and relevant system for all citizens. Key priorities included universalizing elementary education, eradicating illiteracy, and modernizing all levels of education. Several commissions were established to recommend improvements, and policies focused on expanding access, improving quality, and promoting national integration.

Conclusion-

After reviewing the above mentioned historical background of Indian education, it can be concluded that education is greatly influenced by the cultural and political conditions of the society of that time. In the Vedic period, Indian society was integrated with spiritual discipline and human values. That is

why the education of that time was based on spiritual thoughts and high human values. In the post Vedic period, the dominance of Brahminical rituals increased in the society, so in Indian education, importance was given to activities integrated with yajna, anushtan and rituals.

The ritualistic pomp of the later Vedic period like yajna, bali etc. gave rise to a sense of perversion in the society. As a result of this, the environment of love, peace and non-violence created in the Buddhist monasteries and Vihars by the advent of Mahatma Buddha who talked about compassion, benevolence and peace also influenced the education of the society of that time and Buddhist education was initiated. The British government from time to time was to strengthen their roots through education rather than to reform Indian education in accordance with Indianness. But the diplomatic evil intentions of the British government could not remain hidden from the eyes of aware Indian leaders, the result of which emerged in the form of the National Education Movement.

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